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Ranking of Countries by Political Stability

Between 2013 and 2021 the value of political stability decreased on average by a value equal to -20.20%

Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism measures perceptions of likelihood of political instability and/or politically motivated violence, including terrorism. The estimate gives the country's score on the aggregate indicator, in units of a standard normal distribution, ie ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5.

Ranking of countries by value of political stability and absence of terrorism in 2021. Liechtenstein ranks first in value of political stability and absence of terrorism with a value equal to 1.64, followed by Andorra with 1.63, Singapore with 1.49, New Zealand with 1.44, Dominica with 1.39. In the middle of the table are Eswatini with a value of -0.03, Gabon with -0.09 units, Argentina with -0.11, Malawi with -0.11 and Vietnam -0.11, Cambodia with -0.13. The ranking is closed by Libya with -2.37, Iraq with -2.40, Afghanistan with -2.53, Yemen Rep with -2.59, Syrian Arab Republic -2.66, Somalia with -2.68.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the percentage change in political stability and the absence of terrorism between 2013 and 2021. Spain is in first place by the value of the percentage change in political stability equal to an amount of 4,718.29%, followed from Fiji with 1,408.98%, Lao PDR with 976.81%, The Gambia with 460.23%, Sao Tome and Principe with a value of 434.25%. In the middle of the table are Estonia with a value of 0.99%, Japan with an amount of 0.81%, Syria Arab Republic with a value of 0.66%, Micronesia Fed. Sts. With 0.5%, St. Lucia with a value of 0.07%, Tuvalu with a value of 0. Djibouti closes the ranking with a value of -592.12%, Armenia with a value of -856.98%, South Africa with a value of -1,426.26%, Belarus with a value of -12,460.88% and Moldova with a value of -25,517.7%.

Machine learning applied to the prediction of the future value of political stability. The predictive efficiency of the algorithms is analyzed considering the maximization of the R-squared and the minimization of the statistical errors MAE-Mean Average Error, MSE-Mean Squared Error, RMSE-Root Mean Squared Error. 80% of the data is used for the training of the algorithms while the remaining part or 20% is used for the actual prediction. The following ordering of the algorithms is identified below, namely:

- Linear Regression with a payoff value equal to 4;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 8;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value equal to 12;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 16;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 20;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a value of 24;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 28.

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By applying the Linear Regression algorithm, it is possible to predict the future value of political stability in the following countries, namely:

- Ethiopia with a value of 152.41%;
- South Africa with a value of 124.16%;
- Madagascar with a value of 106.11%;
- Turkmenistan with a value of 105.66%;
- Tajikistan with a value of 105.25%;
- Cuba with a value of 104.92%;
- Kenya with a value of 103.9%;
- Ghana with a value of 103.79%;
- Lithuania with a value of 103.24%;
- Vietnam with a value of 102.15%;
- Gambia with a value of 101.18%;
- Luxembourg with a value of 100.93%;
- Ecuador and North Macedonia with a value of 100.73%;
- Saudi Arabia with a value of 100.71%;
- San Marino with a value of 100.24%;
- Denmark with a value of 100.23%;
- Japan with a value of 100.18%;
- Comoros with a value of 100.16%;
- Fiji with a value of 100.12%;
- Antigua and Barbuda with a value of 99.62%;
- St. Vincent and the Grenadines with a value of 99.51%;
- France with a value of 99.35%;
- Netherlands with a value of 99.28%;
- United Kingdom with a value of 98.92%;
- Dominica with a value of 98.68%;
- Eswatini and Lao PDR with a value of 98.11%;
- Niger with a value of 97.75%;
- South Korea with a value of 95.96%;
- Ukraine with a value of 95.85%;
- Türkiye with a value of 95.57%;
- Moldova with 95.44%;
- Burundi with 93.4%;
- Uzbekistan with a value of 93.15%;
- Egypt with a value of 88.55%;
- Central African Republic with 65.71%;
- Libya with a value of 65.31%;
- Afghanistan with a value of -6.71%.

Conclusions. If we look overall at the global distribution of the value of political stability, it appears that Western countries are certainly the most evolved from the point of view of the absence of terrorism and political violence. Certainly the leading countries are the European countries, the Scandinavian countries, the Anglo-Saxon countries and Japan. To these must be added other countries in Asia, Africa and Latin America. For example, in Latin America there are countries that have high levels of political stability such as Germany, Chile, Uruguay, Paraguay, Suriname and Guyana. In Africa, the countries that have the highest level of political stability are Namibia, Botswana, Zambia,

Gabon, Ghana, Liberia and Sierra Leone, Senegal. In the Asian continent, in addition to those already mentioned, there are other countries such as Mongolia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Thailand, Bhutan, Nepal, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan. It must therefore be considered that although there is friction between the Western model of democracy and the rampant Asian autocratic economies, it is clear, at least as regards the dimension of political stability, that Western democracies perform better than Eastern autocracies. Since political stability is a requirement of economic growth then it is very likely that the institutional set-up of Asian countries reduces the ability of Asian countries to be placed on a long-term economic growth path. In fact, foreign direct investment requires the development of international relations based on trust and on investors' request for conditions that can guarantee the persistence of investments even in the worst conditions of the economic cycle. It is therefore necessary that the Asian countries work hard on the institutional front to avoid nullifying the significant economic progress achieved also thanks to the conspicuous investments of Western companies.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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References

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Government Expenditure on Education in the ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4438106.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Determinants of CO2 Emissions in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4425121.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at

World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4388957.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Fight Against Corruption at Global Level. A Metric Approach. A Metric Approach (December 30, 2022).

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis. A Data-Driven Analysis (December 25, 2022).

Laureti, L., Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Renewable Electricity Output on Sustainability in the Context of Circular Economy: A Global Perspective. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2160.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Intellectual Assets in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956755.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232

Appendix

